

30 secondary organic aerosol (SOA) source. This small change is due to the nonlinearity of the system
31 with increases predicted in some areas and decreases in others, but also the cancelation of the
32 effects of the various processes like accelerated growth and accelerated coagulation. Locally, the
33 effects can be significant. For example, an increase in N_{100} by 20-50% is predicted over
34 Scandinavia and significant increases (10-20%) over some parts of central Europe. The ELVOCs
35 contributed on average around $0.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and accounted for 10-15% of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ OA. The addition
36 of IVOC emissions and their aging reactions led to surprising reduction of the total number of
37 particles (N_{tot}) and N_{10} by 10-15 and 5-10%, respectively, and to an increase of the concentration
38 of N_{100} by 5-10%. These were due to the accelerated coagulation and reduced nucleation rates.

39

40 **1. Introduction**

41 Two major processes are responsible for the introduction of new particles in the
42 atmosphere: direct emission from numerous sources and nucleation from low-volatility vapors.
43 New particles formed by nucleation can either grow by condensation of vapors (e.g. sulfuric acid,
44 ammonia, nitric acid, and organics) to larger sizes becoming cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) and
45 thereby may increase the cloud droplet number concentration (CDNC) or affected by coagulation
46 with pre-existing larger particles and be lost (Adams and Seinfeld, 2002). Globally, according to
47 large-scale model simulations, atmospheric new particle formation (NPF) and subsequent particle
48 growth represent the most significant source of atmospheric aerosol particles, at least in terms of
49 their total number concentration (Kulmala et al., 2004; Makkonen et al., 2009; Merikanto et al.,
50 2009; Pierce and Adams, 2009; Wang and Penner, 2009; Yu and Luo, 2009). An increase of the
51 number concentration of particles that may act as CCN results in higher CDNC and brighter clouds
52 with longer lifetimes.

53 Globally, organic particulate matter makes up more than 50% of the sub-micrometer mass
54 concentration of ambient aerosols in locations throughout the world (Kanakidou et al., 2005;
55 Seinfeld and Pandis, 2006; Zhang et al., 2007). Nearly 70% of this material is thought to be
56 secondary organic aerosol (SOA) formed from the oxidation of volatile organic compounds
57 (VOCs) (Hallquist et al., 2009; Schulze et al., 2017). Many of the relevant precursor VOCs are
58 biogenic in origin, such as monoterpenes ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}$) and isoprene (C_5H_8).

59 Several recent field studies have shown that SOA in polluted areas cannot be explained by
60 the simulation of only the first generation of reactions of “traditional” SOA precursors: biogenic

61 compounds (monoterpenes, sesquiterpenes, and isoprene) and anthropogenic compounds
62 (aromatics, olefins and large alkanes) (de Gouw et al., 2005; Volkamer et al., 2006; Kleinman et
63 al., 2008; Docherty et al., 2008; Matsui et al., 2009; Dzepina et al., 2009). At the same time, it has
64 become clear that organic vapors are responsible for most of the new particle growth in
65 environments with low sulfur dioxide levels (Olenius et al., 2018; Yli-Juuti et al., 2020).

66 Traditional treatment of SOA formation considers only VOCs as the precursors and only
67 semivolatile products (Odum et al., 1996). Robinson et al. (2007) suggested that intermediate
68 volatile organic compounds (IVOCs) either emitted directly or resulting from the evaporation of
69 particles may be an important and previously neglected pool of precursors for SOA formation. In
70 addition, later generations of reactions of the products of VOCs, IVOCs and SVOCs can lead to
71 products of even lower volatility and formation of SOA (Donahue et al., 2006). These chemical
72 reactions can lead to continued SOA production after complete precursor consumption as products
73 undergo further oxidation (Kroll et al., 2006; Ng et al., 2006).

74 Secondary extremely low volatile organic compounds (ELVOCs) have been detected both
75 in the ambient atmosphere and laboratory studies (Donahue et al., 2011). These compounds
76 promote new particle growth and CCN production in the atmosphere (Jokinen et al., 2015; Kirkby
77 et al., 2016). ELVOCs can be produced rapidly in the gas phase during monoterpene oxidation
78 (Ehn et al., 2014), and can enhance atmospheric new particle formation and growth (Jokinen et al.,
79 2015). Due to their exceptionally low volatility, ELVOCs condense essentially irreversibly onto
80 growing particles at a rate controlled by the Fuchs-adjusted particle surface area (Shrivastava et
81 al., 2017). The addition of the ELVOCs in PMCAMx-UF increased the effective biogenic SOA
82 yields, becoming an additional source of SOA especially significant at low OA levels. At the same
83 time, the addition of this extra material results in a change in the volatility distribution of the
84 predicted SOA.

85 Fanourgakis et al. (2019) evaluated 16 global chemistry transport models during a 4-year
86 period and compared their prediction to the near-surface observed number concentration of aerosol
87 particles across Europe and Japan. All models tended to underestimate the number concentrations
88 for particles larger with diameter than 50 nm (N_{50}). The normalized mean bias (NMB) was -51%
89 and normalized mean error (NME) was 55% for all stations. Sengupta et al. (2021) used the
90 GLOMAP (Global Model of Aerosol Processes; Spracklen et al., 2005) modal aerosol
91 microphysics model (Mann et al., 2010) simulating the production of six surrogate SOA species

92 from the oxidation of anthropogenic VOCs, monoterpenes, and isoprene. It was assumed that
93 ELVOCs derive only from biogenic sources and can nucleate to form new particles (Gordon et al.,
94 2016). Different values of the ELVOC yield were used and the model predictions were compared
95 to observations of OA mass concentration as well as to the N_3 (particles with diameter larger than
96 3 nm) and N_{50} number concentrations. Concentrations of N_3 and N_{50} were consistently
97 underestimated, while the best model performance (based on the Taylor model skill score) was
98 achieved when the ELVOC yield from precursor VOCs was around 13%. These studies suggest
99 that the role of organics and especially ELVOCs on particle formation and growth is still not well
100 understood.

101 In this study we extend the three-dimensional regional chemical transport model (CTM),
102 PMCAMx-UF (Jung et al., 2010), with detailed aerosol microphysics (Gaydos et al., 2007; Karydis
103 et al., 2007) that has been used and evaluated for simulations over the US and Europe (Fountoukis
104 et al., 2012). The number concentrations of particles with diameter larger than 10 nm (N_{10}) and
105 100 nm (N_{100}) were used for the analysis of the model predictions of Fountoukis et al. (2012),
106 whereas Gordon et al. (2016) relied on N_3 and N_{50} . The N_3 and N_{10} are connected to some extent,
107 but usually there are more reliable measurements available in more sites for N_{10} . The same applies
108 for the N_{50} and N_{100} pair, but the N_{100} is often closer to the CCN sizes at moderate cloud
109 supersaturations. N_{10} and N_{100} were chosen as the metrics in this study for continuity, given that
110 they have been used in previous PMCAMx-UF evaluations.

111 Originally PMCAMx-UF assumed that growth of new particles was exclusively due to
112 sulfuric acid and ammonia condensation while the semi-volatile secondary organics condensed
113 only on the accumulation mode thus contributing to the condensation and coagulation sinks. This
114 initial model version was found to reproduce more than 70% of the hourly number concentrations
115 of N_{10} within a factor of 2 (Fountoukis et al., 2012). However, the concentration of N_{100} as proxy
116 for the number of particles that can act as CCN) was systematically underpredicted. The growth
117 rates were also underpredicted, with smaller errors in sites where the sulfate to organics mass ratio
118 was high. These problems were caused mainly by insufficient organic vapor condensation
119 (Fountoukis et al., 2012) on ultrafine particles. Patoulias et al. (2018) developed an extended
120 version of PMCAMx-UF in which the SOA components were modeled as semi-volatile first-
121 generation products of the oxidation of VOCs. The model predictions were compared against size
122 distribution measurements from 16 stations in Europe during a photochemically active period.

123 Including SOA condensation on ultrafines in PMCAMx-UF improved its ability to reproduce the
124 N_{10} and N_{100} concentration at ground level. The inclusion of SOA decreased the daily normalized
125 mean bias (NMB) of N_{10} from 85% to 75% and the daily NMB of N_{100} from 40% to 20%. However,
126 the results suggested that there is a need for additional improvements.

127 The primary goal of this study is to examine the role of IVOCs and ELVOCs on particle
128 number concentrations in Europe. PMCAMx-UF is extended to simulate the multiple generations
129 of IVOC gas-phase oxidation and the production of ELVOCs by monoterpenes. This extended
130 version is used for the base case simulations in this study. The model predictions are compared
131 with measurements from 26 sites during the intensive field campaign that took place in Europe, as
132 part of the Pan-European-Gas-AeroSOI-climate-interaction Study (PEGASOS) project, from June
133 5 to July 8, 2012. The airborne data obtained by a Zeppelin measuring above Po-Valley during the
134 same campaign are also used. An analysis of the Zeppelin measurement can be found in Lampilahti
135 et al. (2021). Additional simulations are performed neglecting certain processes (e.g., production
136 of ELVOCs) to quantify their role in the model predictions.

137

138 **2. Model description**

139 PMCAMx-UF is a three-dimensional chemical transport model (CTM) that simulates the
140 aerosol number size distribution in addition to the mass/composition size distribution (Jung et al.,
141 2010; Fountoukis et al., 2012) and is described in detail in Patoulias et al. (2018). PMCAMx-UF
142 is based on the framework of PMCAMx (Gaydos et al., 2007; Karydis et al., 2007), describing the
143 processes of horizontal and vertical advection, emissions, horizontal and vertical dispersion, wet
144 and dry deposition, aqueous and aerosol phase chemistry, as well as aerosol dynamics and
145 thermodynamics.

146 For the simulation of aerosol microphysics, PMCAMx-UF uses the updated version of
147 DMANx which simulates the processes of coagulation, condensation/evaporation and nucleation
148 (Patoulias et al., 2015) with the two-moment aerosol sectional (TOMAS) algorithm (Adams and
149 Seinfeld, 2002; Jung et al., 2006). A key feature of TOMAS is its ability to track two independent
150 moments of the aerosol size distribution for each size bin: the aerosol number and mass
151 concentration.

152 The aerosol size distribution is discretized into 41 sections covering the diameter range from
153 approximately 0.8 nm to 10 μm . The lowest boundary is at 3.75×10^{-25} kg of dry aerosol mass per

154 particle. Each successive boundary has twice the mass of the previous one. The particle
155 components modeled include sulfate, ammonium, nitrate, sodium, chloride, crustal material,
156 water, elemental carbon, primary organic aerosol (POA) and eight surrogate SOA components.

157 In this work, the nucleation rate is calculated using a scaled ternary parameterization based
158 on the original expressions of Napari et al. (2002) with a scaling factor of 10^{-6} following the
159 suggestions of Fountoukis et al. (2012). The binary parameterization of Vehkamäki et al. (2002)
160 is employed if the NH_3 concentration is below a threshold value of 0.01 ppt.

161 Coagulation of particles in the atmosphere is an important sink of aerosol number but is
162 also a mechanism by which freshly nucleated particles grow to larger sizes. Following Adams and
163 Seinfeld (2002), TOMAS assumes that the aerosol particles coagulate via Brownian diffusion and
164 that the effects of gravitational settling and turbulence on coagulation are negligible. The
165 calculation of the coagulation coefficients is based on the wet diameters of the particles. These wet
166 diameters are calculated following the approach of Gaydos et al. (2005). For small particles (<100
167 nm), we use the expression of Dahneke et al. (1983) to correct for non-continuum effects. The
168 coagulation algorithm uses an adaptive time step. The time step is limited so that the aerosol
169 number or mass concentration in any size category does not increase by more than an order of
170 magnitude or decrease by more than 25% in each step.

171 The extended SAPRC (Statewide Air Pollution Research Center) chemical mechanism
172 (Carter, 2000; Environ, 2003), which includes 219 reactions of 64 gases and 18 free radicals, is
173 used for the gas phase chemistry mechanism in PMCAMx-UF. The SAPRC version used for this
174 work includes five lumped alkanes (ALK1-5), two lumped olefins (OLE1-2), two lumped
175 aromatics (ARO1-2), isoprene (ISOP), a lumped monoterpene (TERP) and a lumped sesquiterpene
176 species (SESQ).

177 Condensation of gas-phase species to existing aerosol particles is an important source of
178 aerosol mass and a means by which small particles grow to CCN sizes. Sulfuric acid is assumed
179 to be in pseudo-steady state in PMCAMx-UF. This pseudo steady-state approximation (PSSA) for
180 sulfuric acid proposed by Pierce and Adams (2009) increases the computational speed with a small
181 loss in accuracy. Jung et al. (2010) evaluated the performance of PSSA for sulfuric acid in DMAN
182 against a 4th order Runge-Kutta algorithm and showed that PSSA was accurate and
183 computationally efficient. Condensation of ammonia is simulated following the approach

184 described by Jung et al. (2006). Ammonia condensation on the ultrafine particles ends when sulfate
185 is fully neutralized to ammonium sulfate.

186 Nitric and hydrochloric acids partition to particles (as nitrate and chloride, respectively) in
187 the accumulation mode range in PMCAMx-UF assuming that the system is always in equilibrium.
188 The amounts of nitric acid and hydrochloric acid transferred at each time step between the gas and
189 aerosol phases are determined by applying the aerosol thermodynamic model ISORROPIA (Nenes
190 et al., 1998). This amount is then distributed over the aerosol size sections by using weighting
191 factors based on their effective surface area (Pandis et al., 1993).

192 PMCAMx-UF assumes that organics and inorganics are in different phases in the same
193 particles. Therefore, the condensation of one affects the size distribution of the particles and
194 therefore the condensation rate of the other. The inorganic aerosol thermodynamics including the
195 sulfate/bisulfate split and the water uptake by all inorganic aerosol components are simulated by
196 ISORROPIA. The water content of the organic aerosol is neglected in this version of PMCAMx-
197 UF and the aerosol water is dominated by the inorganic aerosol components. Additional
198 information can be found in previous publications describing the evolution of PMCAMx-UF (Jung
199 et al. 2010; Fountoukis et al. 2012; Patoulias et al. 2018).

200

201 **2.1 Secondary organic aerosol formation**

202 Gas-phase oxidation of VOCs produces semi-volatile and low-volatility products that can
203 then condense to the particle phase. The volatility-basis set (VBS) framework used in PMCAMx-
204 UF (Donahue et al., 2006) describes the volatility distribution of the OA compounds. SOA is
205 formed from anthropogenic (aSOA) and biogenic (bSOA) precursors. Each of these types is
206 simulated with 5 volatility bins with saturation concentrations of 10^{-5} , 1, 10, 100 and $1000 \mu\text{g}$
207 m^{-3} . The $10^{-5} \mu\text{g} \text{m}^{-3}$ bin was added in this work to describe the ELVOCs. We assumed an average
208 molecular weight of 200 g mol^{-1} for SOA, and an effective enthalpy of vaporization of 30 kJ
209 mol^{-1} (Pathak et al., 2007; Stanier et al., 2007). The SOA yields used in this version of PMCAMx-
210 UF for the semi-volatile components are the NO_x -dependent stoichiometric yields of Murphy et
211 al. (2009).

212 Chemical reactions that change the volatility of the organics in the gas phase will change
213 the OA mass by influencing their partitioning. In PMCAMx-UF all secondary species are treated
214 as chemically reactive. Further gas-phase oxidation of OA vapors (chemical aging) is modeled

215 using a second-order reaction with hydroxyl radicals and a rate constant equal to $1 \times 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^3$
216 $\text{molecule}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Atkinson and Arey, 2003). Each reaction is assumed to reduce the volatility of the
217 vapor material by one order of magnitude (i.e., shifting material from a C^* of 100 to $10 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$),
218 with a small increase in mass (7.5%) to account for the added oxygen (Lane et al., 2008;
219 Shrivastava et al., 2008). IVOCs were not included in the original emission inventory and therefore
220 have been added to the emissions. The IVOC emission rate is estimated based on the non-volatile
221 POA emissions included in the inventory and is assumed to be 1.5 times the non-volatile POA
222 emissions. IVOCs are distributed in the 10^3 , 10^4 , 10^5 , and $10^6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ saturation concentration bins
223 and their emission rates are assumed to be equal to 0.3, 0.4, 0.5 and 0.8 times the original non-
224 volatile POA emission rate, for the 10^3 - 10^6 bins respectively (Robinson et. 2007).

225 ELVOCs were assumed to be produced by the oxidation of monoterpenes with a molar
226 yield of 5%. For comparison, ELVOCs yields for the α -pinene ozonolysis in Jokinen et al. (2015)
227 were $3.4 \pm 1.7\%$, by Ehn et al. (2014) of $7 \pm 4\%$ and $4.5 \pm 3.8\%$ in Rissanen et al. (2014). An
228 average molecular weight of 200 g mol^{-1} for ELVOCs was assumed in this work.

229 The partitioning of OA between the gas and particulate phases is simulated dynamically in
230 PMCAMx-UF without assuming equilibrium (Patoulias et al., 2015). The driving force for
231 condensation of a vapor to an aerosol particle is the difference between its ambient vapor partial
232 pressure and the equilibrium vapor pressure over the particles, with the latter including the Kelvin
233 effect which is due to the curvature of the particles. The Kelvin effect is larger for the smaller
234 particles and acts as a barrier for the condensation of organic vapors on these particles. In this
235 simulation a surface tension of $\sigma=0.025 \text{ N m}^{-1}$ is assumed for all SOA components (Pierce et al.,
236 2011; Patoulias et al. 2015).

237 Three different chemical schemes are used in this work (Table 1). The first scheme (case
238 1 or base case) includes (i) the aging of SOA components from anthropogenic sources, using a rate
239 constant $k(298 \text{ K}) = 10 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ molecule}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (anthropogenic SOA aging), (ii) the aging of
240 IVOCs using a rate constant $k(298 \text{ K}) = 40 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ molecule}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, (iii) production of ELVOCs
241 with saturation concentration of $10^{-5} \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ from the oxidation of monoterpenes with a yield of
242 5%. The aSOA aging rate constant is based on OH oxidation of the products of aromatic VOCs
243 oxidation (Atkinson 2000; 2003). No biogenic SOA aging was simulated in this case, an
244 assumption based on laboratory studies (Presto et al., 2006; Ng et al., 2006) and the results of Lane
245 et al. (2008). In the second simulation (case 2), the ELVOC yield was set to zero thus neglecting

246 their formation. The rest of the parameters were the same as in the base case. Finally, in the third
247 simulation the emissions of IVOCs and the chemical aging reactions of all VOCs were neglected
248 while the production of the ELVOCs was simulated similarly to the base case.

249

250 **2.2 Model application and measurements**

251 The PMCAMx-UF modeling domain in this application covers a $5400 \times 5832 \text{ km}^2$ region
252 in Europe, with a $36 \times 36 \text{ km}$ grid resolution and 14 vertical layers extending up to approximately
253 7.2 km. The modeling period covers 34 days, from June 5 to July 8, 2012 corresponding to the
254 PEGASOS 2012 intensive period. PMCAMx-UF was set to perform simulations on a rotated polar
255 stereographic map projection. The first two days of each simulation were excluded from the
256 analysis to minimize the effect of the initial conditions on the results. For the boundary conditions,
257 constant and relatively low values have been used (Table S1) so that the predicted particle number
258 concentrations over central Europe are determined for all practical purposes by the emissions and
259 corresponding processes simulated by the model. The boundary conditions are identical to those
260 used in Patoulias et al. (2018). The effect of these boundary conditions on the predicted number
261 concentrations are discussed in Patoulias et al. (2018).

262 Meteorological inputs to PMCAMx-UF include horizontal wind components, vertical
263 diffusivity, temperature, pressure, water vapor, clouds, and rainfall. The Weather Research and
264 Forecasting (WRF) model (Skamarock et al., 2005) was used to generate the above inputs. WRF
265 was driven by geographical and dynamic meteorological data generated by the Global Forecast
266 System (GFSv15) of the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration/National Centers for
267 Environmental Prediction. Each layer of PMCAMx-UF was aligned with the layers used in WRF.
268 The WRF simulation was periodically re-initialized every 3 days with observed conditions to
269 ensure accuracy in the corresponding fields used as inputs in PMCAMx-UF. The measurements
270 were pre-processed by the WPS (WRF Preprocessing System) package, which provides each
271 atmospheric and static field with fidelity appropriate to the chosen grid resolution of the model.
272 The performance of WRF for Europe against observed meteorological variables has been the topic
273 of several recent studies (Jimenez-Guerrero et al., 2008; de Meij et al., 2009; Im et al., 2010;
274 Argueso et al., 2011; Garcia-Diez et al., 2012) demonstrating good performance.

275 The particle emissions were based on the pan-European anthropogenic particle number
276 emission inventory (Denier van der Gon et al., 2009; Kulmala et al., 2011) and the carbonaceous

277 aerosol inventory (Kulmala et al., 2011) developed during the EUCAARI (European Integrated
278 project on Aerosol, Cloud, Climate, and Air Quality Interactions) project. The resulting
279 number/mass inventories includes both number emissions and consistent size-resolved
280 composition for particles over the size range of approximately 10 nm to 10 μm . Hourly gridded
281 anthropogenic and biogenic emissions included both gases and primary particulate matter. The
282 natural emissions include both particulate matter and gases and combine three different data sets:
283 emissions from ecosystems based on the Model of Emissions of Gases and Aerosols from Nature
284 (MEGAN; Guenther et al., 2006), marine emissions based on the model of O'Dowd et al. (2008)
285 as sea surface covers a considerable area of the domain, and wildfire emissions (Sofiev et al.,
286 2008a, b). MEGAN uses as inputs the plant functional type, the leaf area index, various chemical
287 species emission factors and weather data provided by the WRF. Wind speed fields from WRF
288 and chlorophyll-a concentrations were used as inputs of the marine aerosol model. VOCs were
289 speciated based on the approach proposed by Visschedijk et al. (2007). Anthropogenic gas
290 emissions included land emissions from the GEMS (global and regional Earth-system monitoring
291 using satellite and in-situ data) dataset (Visschedijk et al., 2007). The international shipping,
292 industrial, domestic, agricultural and traffic aerosol emission sources were included in the
293 anthropogenic inventory (Denier van der Gon et al., 2009; Kulmala et al., 2011).

294 The model results were compared against measurements in 26 ground sites, which are
295 available in the European Supersites for Atmospheric Aerosol Research (EUSAAR), and EBAS
296 databases (<https://ebas.nilu.no>) and the Aerosols, Clouds and Trace gases Research Infrastructure
297 (ACTRIS) (<https://actris.nilu.no>). Particle size distribution measurements at all sites were made
298 using either a Differential Mobility Particle Sizer (DMPS) or a Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer
299 (SMPS). Information about all stations can be found in Table S2.

300 An intensive field campaign took place in Europe, as part of the Pan-European-Gas-
301 AeroSOI-climate-interaction Study (PEGASOS) project, from June 5 to July 8, 2012.
302 Measurements of aerosol mass concentration PM_1 (particulate matter particles of diameter less
303 than 1 micrometer) from the PEGASOS project are also available for the same period for Patras
304 (Greece), Finokalia (Greece), San Pietro Capofiume (Italy) and Bologna (Italy) (Table S3a) and
305 filter $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ (particulate matter particles of diameter less than 2.5 micrometer) measurements from
306 6 additional stations in Europe (Table S3b). The organic aerosol mass concentration was estimated

307 from the organic carbon measurements assuming an organic mass to carbon ratio equal to 1.8
308 (Kostenidou et al., 2015).

309 The measurement of organic carbon and therefore the estimated OA using filters is
310 characterized by two main artifacts: a positive one involving adsorption of organic vapors on the
311 quartz filters used for the sampling and a negative one related to the evaporation of some of the
312 semi-volatile material (Turpin et al., 2000; Mikuška et al., 2011). There is a rich literature on the
313 magnitude of these artifacts and on ways to minimize them or correct for them (involving denuders
314 for removal of organic vapors and after-filters). In this work, we use the reported measurements
315 for the model evaluation keeping in mind their uncertainty.

316 The airborne measurements acquired by the PEGASOS Zeppelin were acquired during the
317 simulation period over the Po Valley. The Po Valley region is situated between the Alps in the
318 north and the Apennines Mountains in the south–southwest. The mountains surround the valley on
319 three sides and high levels of pollutants are often observed in the region due to the industrial,
320 agricultural, and other anthropogenic emissions. In addition, emissions from ship traffic on the
321 Adriatic Sea (Hamed et al., 2007) and long-range transport from central-eastern Europe also
322 contribute pollutants to the region (Sogacheva et al., 2007). A SMPS was used to measure the
323 number size distribution of particles in the size range of 10 to 430 nm. Details of the relevant
324 PEGASOS Zeppelin measurements can be found in Lampilahti et al. (2021).

325

326 **3. Results**

327 **3.1 Base case**

328 The average predicted ground level average number concentrations for the total number of
329 particles (N_{tot}) and for particles with diameters above 10 nm (N_{10}), 50 nm (N_{50}) and 100 nm (N_{100}),
330 during June 5 to July 8, 2012 are shown in Figure 1. The N_{50} and N_{100} concentrations are often
331 used as proxies for CCN number concentrations (Fountoukis et al., 2012). On a domain average
332 basis, the model predicted for the ground level 4780 cm^{-3} for N_{tot} , 3630 cm^{-3} for N_{10} , 1990 cm^{-3}
333 for N_{50} , and 820 cm^{-3} for N_{100} during the simulated period. The highest N_{tot} average concentrations
334 (more than 15000 cm^{-3}) were predicted over Bulgaria, southern Romania, Turkey, Poland,
335 Holland, Portugal, Northern Spain, Eastern UK and Russia. On the other hand, the highest N_{50} and
336 N_{100} are predicted over the Mediterranean, mainly in areas near Southern Spain, Southern Italy,
337 and the Balkans. The N_{tot} and N_{10} are high in areas of frequent nucleation events and areas with

338 high particle number emissions, whereas the N_{50} and N_{100} levels are affected significantly by
339 secondary particulate matter production. The high photochemical activity over the Eastern
340 Mediterranean leads to the corresponding high levels of N_{50} and N_{100} during this period.

341

342 **3.2 Evaluation of PMCAMx-UF predictions**

343 **3.2.1 Comparison of PMCAMx-UF predictions to ground aerosol number observations**

344 The prediction skill metrics of PMCAMx-UF, for the daily average ground measurements
345 from the 26 stations, are summarized in Tables 2 and 3 for both the base case and the case in which
346 the ELVOCs are neglected.

347 For the base case simulation, the model has a tendency to overestimate the N_{10} levels. The
348 normalized mean bias (NMB) for the daily average concentrations is 23% and the normalized
349 mean error (NME) 63%. The N_{10} was overpredicted in 18 sites, underpredicted in 7 and there was
350 practically zero bias (less than 0.1%) in the last station. The NMB in 8 sites (Prague-Suchdol,
351 Ispra, Melpitz, Patras, K-Puszt, Hohenpeissenberg, Hyytiälä and San Pietro Capofiume) was less
352 than $\pm 15\%$, and for another 8 stations between $\pm 15\%$ and $\pm 40\%$ (Annaberg-Buchholz, Cabauw,
353 Dresden Nord and Winkelmannstrasse, Finokalia, Giordan Lighthouse, Kosetice, Montseny and
354 Varrio). The highest discrepancies with the measurements of N_{10} were found in Aspvreten,
355 Birkness II, Usti n.L.-mesto, Vavihill, Vielsalm, Zugspitze-Schneefernerhaus, Waldhof, Costa
356 Navarino, and Thessaloniki with NMB higher than $\pm 40\%$.

357 The model performed better for N_{100} . There was little bias in the corresponding predictions
358 on average (the NMB was -10%) and the NME was 45%. The NMB for 10 sites (Cabauw, Giordan
359 Lighthouse, Hyytiälä, Kosetice, Melpitz, Patras, Prague-Suchdol, Vielsalm, Waldhof and
360 Zugspitze) was less than $\pm 15\%$ and for another 12 (Annaberg-Buchholz, Birkenes II, Dresden
361 Nord and Winkelmannstrasse, Finokalia, Hohenpeissenberg, Ispra, K-Puszt, Montseny, Costa
362 Navarino, San Pietro Capofiume, Usti n.L.-mesto. and Vavihill) between $\pm 15\%$ and $\pm 40\%$ (Table
363 3). The absolute NMB for N_{100} exceeded 40% only in Aspvreten, Varrio and Thessaloniki.

364 **3.3.2 Evaluation of aerosol composition predictions**

365 The PMCAMx-UF predictions can be evaluated during that period using available PM_{10}
366 measurements from Aerosol Mass Spectrometers at four stations (Bologna and San Pietro
367 Capofiume, in Italy and Finokalia and Patras, in Greece) that were part of the PEGASOS
368 campaign.

369 In Italy and Greece, the model reproduces the observations of the PM_{10} concentrations of
370 the major inorganic aerosol components (sulfate, ammonium, nitrate) reasonably well (Table 4).
371 The model tends to underpredict the organic aerosol concentrations in Patras and Bologna, while
372 it overpredicts the OA in Finokalia and San Pietro Capofiume (Table 5). The OA NMB is -2% and
373 the NME is 38%, with the Finokalia site presenting the higher NMB value (50%) and San Pietro
374 Capofiume, Bologna the lower ($\pm 20\%$) (Table 5).

375 For the rest of Europe, $PM_{2.5}$ filter measurements have been used, available in the European
376 Supersites for Atmospheric Aerosol Research (EUSAAR) and EBAS databases
377 (<http://ebas.nilu.no/>) for stations that had available data for more than 15 days during the simulated
378 period (6 additional stations in Europe: Payerne, Melpitz, Montseny, Ispra, Diabla Gora, and
379 Iskrba; Table 6). For the calculation of OA mass concentration, we assumed OA:OC=1.8
380 (Kostenidou et al., 2015). For these sites, the model has a tendency towards overestimating the
381 $PM_{2.5}$ OA concentration for 4 out of 6 stations, presenting an average NMB of 20% and NME of
382 62% (Table 6).

383 **3.3.3 Comparison of PMCAMx-UF predictions to Zeppelin measurements**

384 One of the challenges of the PMCAMx-UF evaluation using airborne measurements is that
385 the model predictions are available every 15 min while the corresponding measurements by the
386 Zeppelin were taken every 3 min in different heights. For comparison purposes, the model output
387 was interpolated to the times of the Zeppelin measurement periods. PMCAMx-UF reproduced
388 more than 75% of the 2000 3-min N_{10} and N_{100} measurements by the Zeppelin with a factor of 2
389 (Figure S1). The vertical profiles shown in Fig.2, are averages of different flights that collected
390 data in different days and different altitudes each time. The number of samples at different altitudes
391 changed for each flight creating additional variability in the measured profiles.

392 To facilitate the comparison between measurements and predictions the corresponding
393 average profiles (matched in space and time) were calculated using 80 m altitude bins for all the
394 PEGASOS flights. PMCAMx-UF reproduced on average the N_{10} measurements over Po Valley at
395 the lower 160 m and above 400 m but underestimated the higher N_{10} levels measured in the residual
396 layer at heights between 160-400 m at several of the flights that started several hours before sunrise
397 (Fig. 2a). The average measured N_{10} at all heights was $6,000 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, while the predicted
398 concentration was equal to $4,700 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. PMCAMx-UF reproduced well the N_{100} concentration at
399 all heights (Fig 2b). The model also reproduced 80% of the 3-min N_{100} Zeppelin measurements

400 within a factor of 2. The measured average N_{100} at all heights was $1,500 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and the average
401 predicted by PMCAMx-UF was $1,800 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The ability of the revised model to reproduce
402 reasonably well the high-time resolution (3-minute) Zeppelin measurements at multiple altitudes
403 and locations is encouraging. The predictions of PMCAMx-UF for the aerosol mass concentration
404 were compared to the Zeppelin PM_1 composition measurements obtained by an AMS (each 3
405 minutes, 9 flights, ~1300 data points). The average vertical profiles of organics, sulfate,
406 ammonium, and nitrate are shown in Fig. S2. Overall, the model performance aloft was quite
407 similar with that at the ground level. For example, for the 9 Zeppelin flights the OA normalized
408 mean bias was -4% and the normalized mean error equal to 40% (Table S4). The measured and
409 the predicted OA mean values are 4.6 and $4.4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, respectively.

410

411 **3.2 Effect of ELVOC production on particle number and OA concentrations**

412 An additional simulation was performed neglecting the production of ELVOCs from
413 terpenes (case 2). The addition of ELVOCs, increased the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ OA mass by approximately as
414 much as $0.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Central/Eastern Europe and Russia, accounting for approximately 10-15%
415 of the OA (Fig. 3). In these areas a combination of high terpene emissions and high photochemical
416 reaction rates existed during the simulated period. The highest relative predicted increase of OA
417 was 15-25% in northern Europe. In central Europe the ELVOC formation increased average OA
418 by approximately 10%.

419 The average fractional increase of N_x , due to the production of ELVOCs is calculated as:

$$420 \quad f_{Nx} = \frac{N_x(\text{with ELVOCs}) - N_x(\text{without ELVOCs})}{N_x(\text{without ELVOCs})} \quad (1)$$

421 where, x , is 10, 50, 100 nm or zero (total number). Rather surprisingly, the average fractional
422 change for all number concentrations (N_{tot} , N_{10} , N_{50} and N_{100} ,) is small ranging between 1% and -
423 4% (Fig. 4) (N_{tot} : -8 cm^{-3} or -0.14%, N_{10} : 40 cm^{-3} or -1.14%, N_{50} : 60 cm^{-3} or 3 %, N_{100} : 35 cm^{-3} or
424 4%). One reason for the small average change is that both increases and decreases are predicted
425 for different areas in Europe. These mixed results are due to the fact that the ELVOC condensation
426 accelerates the growth of new and preexisting particles to larger sizes, but at the same time
427 accelerates their losses due to the increase of the coagulation sink and decreases the nucleation
428 rate due to the increase of the condensation sink.

429 The formation of ELVOCs resulted in a predicted decrease of N_{tot} by 20% ($300\text{-}600 \text{ cm}^{-3}$)
430 in parts of the Nordic countries and by 5% in central Europe (Fig. 4). The decreases are predicted

431 for most Europe with the exception of a few areas in which increases are predicted (northern
432 Iberian Peninsula, parts of France, areas in the Balkans with high sulfur dioxide levels, etc.) (Fig.
433 5). The predicted N_{10} increased by 5-15% ($150-400 \text{ cm}^{-3}$) over Finland, northwestern Russia,
434 France, Ireland and northern Portugal. At the same time there were small decreases of a few percent
435 over several areas in Europe especially in the south and in the east as well over the Baltic Sea. N_{50}
436 increased over almost of Europe by 50 to 300 cm^{-3} . This N_{50} increase corresponds to 20-40% over
437 Scandinavia and northwestern Russia, and 10% for central Europe. Finally, the ELVOCs caused
438 an increase in N_{100} of 20-50% over Scandinavia and 10-20% increases over central Europe. The
439 absolute corresponding N_{100} changes in these areas are $100-200 \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

440 The corresponding changes of the number concentrations for particles with diameters
441 between 1 and 10 nm (N_{1-10}), 10 and 50 nm (N_{10-50}) and (iii) 50 and 100 nm (N_{50-100}) are
442 summarized in Fig. S3. These figures illustrate the complex effect of the ELVOCs on different
443 parts of the aerosol number distribution. Decreases in the concentrations of the 1-10 nm particles
444 (decreasing nucleation rate due to increased condensation sink, increasing coagulation with larger
445 particles), increases in the concentrations of the particles with diameter larger than 100 nm (due to
446 accelerated growth of the sub-100 nm particles to larger sizes) and both increases and decreases in
447 the 10-50 nm size range depending on the magnitude of the different competing processes in each
448 area. The effect of the ELVOCs in this PMCAMx simulation is clearly a lot more complex than a
449 uniform increase of particle number concentrations.

450 The spatial variability of the fractional change in the number concentration of N_{1-10}
451 (reflecting nucleation rates), sulfuric acid concentration, condensational sink (CS) and coagulation
452 sink due to the ELVOCs is depicted in Figure S4. In areas such as the Scandinavian Peninsula the
453 production of ELVOCs is predicted to lead to a 20-30% average increase of the coagulation and
454 condensational sinks and a corresponding decrease of sulfuric acid levels and N_{1-10} . Similar
455 changes are predicted for several other areas (e.g., Central Europe) but are less pronounced.

456 The results in the Hyytiälä station in Finland were examined in more detail because the
457 predicted number concentrations in Finland are quite sensitive, according to PMCAMx-UF, to the
458 addition of the ELVOCs. The predicted N_3 , N_{10} , N_{50} and N_{100} concentrations for the base case are
459 in reasonable agreement with the field measurements in this area (Figure S5), with a tendency of
460 the model to overpredict the N_3 levels during a few nucleation events. For all concentrations the
461 simulation with the ELVOCs (base case) reproduces the measurements better than the simulation

462 in which they are neglected. The condensation sink for Hyytiälä increases by a few percent due to
463 the additional mass of the ELVOCs (Figure S5). The average measured and predicted number size
464 distributions in Hyytiälä are shown in Figure S6. The addition of the ELVOCs leads to increased
465 levels in the part of the size distribution above 50 nm. A decrease of the concentration of particles
466 with diameter below 7 nm is predicted due to the addition of the ELVOCs because of both
467 increased coagulation losses but also lower nucleation rates. The difference in the predictions of
468 the two simulations (with and without ELVOCs) in Hyytiälä is modest. The discrepancy between
469 model predictions and measurements is due to both weaknesses of the measurements (particles
470 smaller than 3 nm were not measured) and a tendency of the model to overpredict nucleation event
471 intensity in this area.

472 The ELVOC addition played a minor role on the overall performance of PMCAM_x-UF. The
473 NMB for N_{10} decreased (in absolute terms) by 1%, it increased by 5% for N_{100} due to the addition
474 of the ELVOCs in the simulation (Table 2-3). The addition of the ELVOCs affects mainly the
475 PMCAM_x-UF predictions in northern Europe and especially Finland, where the predictions of
476 N_{100} significantly improve. In Hyytiälä the NMB decreases from -34% to -14% and in Varrio drops
477 from -72% to -49% (Table 3). The corresponding normalized mean errors changed by 1-2%. These
478 small changes in the performance metrics are consistent with the small overall changes caused by
479 the ELVOC addition.

480 The small change in the OA mass concentration due to the addition of the ELVOCs has a
481 modest impact on the performance of PMCAM_x-UF for OA (Table S5 and S6). For example, the
482 PM₁ OA bias improves from -6% to 2% while the PM_{2.5} OA bias increases from 15% to 20%. The
483 changes in normalized error are 1% or less.

484

485 **3.3 Effect of IVOCs on particle number concentrations**

486 The emissions of IVOCs ($C^* \geq 10^{-3} \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) were set to zero in a sensitivity test (Case 3) to
487 quantify their effect on the predicted particle number concentration and size distribution. The
488 SOA formed by the IVOCs (SOA-iv) exceeds $1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in southern Europe, over the Mediterranean
489 Sea, but also in large areas over central and eastern Europe (Fig. 6). The high SOA-iv levels over
490 the Mediterranean are due to the oxidation of IVOCs emitted from large wildfires that occurred
491 during the simulation period. The corresponding SOA-iv is 10-25% of the total OA over

492 continental Europe and even higher (about 60%) over parts of the marine atmosphere. The average
493 fractional increase of N_x , due to emission and aging of IVOCs is calculated as:

$$494 \quad f_{N_x} = \frac{N_x(\text{with IVOCs}) - N_x(\text{without IVOCs})}{N_x(\text{without IVOCs})} \quad (2)$$

495 where, x , is 10, 50, 100 nm or zero (total number).

496 According to PMCAM_x-UF the addition of the emissions of IVOCs and their aging
497 reactions lead to a reduction of N_{tot} by 5-10% and N_{10} by 5% (Fig. 7) for continental Europe. On
498 the other hand, this addition of IVOCs leads to an increase of N_{50} by 5% and N_{100} by 5-10% mainly
499 in central Europe and the Mediterranean Sea (Fig. 7). The corresponding changes of the number
500 concentrations for the various size ranges N_{1-10} , N_{10-50} and N_{50-100} are summarized in Fig. 8. The
501 predicted N_{1-10} decreases approximately 15-20% for most of Europe except for the Scandinavian
502 peninsula due to the IVOCs. N_{10-50} decreases 10-15% mainly in southern Europe and N_{50-100}
503 changes less than $\pm 5\%$ or $\pm 100 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ in the simulated domain.

504 The atmospheric oxidation of the emitted IVOCs produces semi-volatile organic
505 compounds, which condense preferentially on particles in the accumulation mode and not so much
506 on the smallest particles due to the Kelvin effect. This results in an increase of both the
507 condensation and coagulation sinks, which then lead to a decrease of the nucleation rate but also
508 on the coagulation rate of the smaller with the larger particles.

509 The effect of the addition of the IVOCs on the performance of PMCAM_x-UF is modest and
510 mixed. The NMB for N_{10} increased by 4% (from 23% to 27%) and decreased by 5% for N_{100} (from
511 10% to 5%) (Table S7). The corresponding NME for both N_{10} and N_{100} changed slightly
512 (approximately 1%). The modest overall changes on the number distribution of the ultrafine
513 particles caused by the addition of IVOCs and the corresponding aging reactions are consistent
514 with the small changes in the PMCAM_x-UF performance metrics.

515 The addition of the IVOCs and the resulting SOA-iv from their oxidation also had mixed
516 results in the PMCAM_x-UF performance for OA in Europe. This added SOA removed the
517 underprediction of OA against the AMS measurements in Italy and Greece; the NMB changed
518 from -18% when IVOCs were neglected to 2% when IVOCs were included (Table S8). The NME
519 decreased a little (from 38% to 35%) with the IVOC addition. The performance against the OA
520 measurements in the other European sites became a little worse when IVOCs were included in the
521 model (Table S9). The small underprediction (NMB=-8%) in OA became a larger overprediction
522 (NMB=20%) and the NME increased from 50% to 62%. These results are characteristic of the

523 uncertainties in primary OA emissions but also SOA production from the various VOCs and
524 IVOCs emitted by anthropogenic and biogenic sources.

525

526 **4. Conclusions**

527 A new version of PMCAMx-UF was developed with the ability to simulate the formation
528 and dynamic condensation of ELVOCs during the oxidation of the monoterpenes and the
529 emissions and multi-generational chemistry of IVOCs. The model was applied to the PEGASOS
530 summer intensive period campaign during the summer of 2012. The available measurements
531 included both ground stations across Europe and airborne measurements from a Zeppelin over the
532 Po Valley.

533 The number concentration predictions of PMCAMx-UF, are compared against ground
534 measurements from 26 stations in Europe. The model tends to overestimate daily average N_{10} with
535 a normalized bias of 35% and an average error of 64%. PMCAMx-UF performed well for N_{100}
536 with a low bias (-2 %) and an error of 41%. The performance of the model in the lowest 1 km of
537 the atmosphere above Po Valley for both N_{10} and N_{100} was even better than its average performance
538 over Europe. The model's predicted PM_{10} and $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations and composition had NMB of
539 15% and errors less than 60% depending on the PM component. These results suggest that
540 PMCAMx-UF does a reasonable job reproducing the aerosol mass and number concentrations over
541 Europe during the simulated period.

542 The ELVOCs produced by the monoterpene oxidation contributed, according to the
543 PMCAMx-UF predictions on average around $0.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and accounted for 10-15% of the $PM_{2.5}$
544 OA. The highest relative predicted increase of OA was 15-25% in northern Europe, while the
545 ELVOC formation increased average OA by approximately 10% in central Europe.

546 The ELVOC production by monoterpenes led to surprisingly small changes of the average
547 number concentrations over Europe. The total number concentration decreased by 0.2%, the N_{10}
548 decreases by 1.1%, while N_{50} increased by 3% and N_{100} by 4% due to this new SOA source. One
549 of the reasons for these small average increases is the nonlinearity of the system leading to both
550 increases and decreases in different parts of Europe. Even if ELVOCs accelerate the growth of the
551 newly formed particles to larger sizes increasing in this way their lifetime, at the same time they
552 increase the aerosol mass and surface area as they mostly condense on the accumulation mode.
553 Therefore, they increase the condensation sink, decreasing the sulfuric acid supersaturation and

554 the corresponding nucleation rate. They also increase the coagulation sink and thus accelerate the
555 removal of all nanoparticles.

556 Locally the effects of the ELVOC production could be higher. For example, it is estimated
557 that the ELVOC productions leads to a decrease of the total particle concentration N_{tot} by 20% in
558 parts of the Nordic countries and by 5% in central Europe. At the same time, the predicted N_{10}
559 increased by 5-15% ($150-400 \text{ cm}^{-3}$) over Finland, northwestern Russia, France, Ireland and
560 northern Portugal due to these secondary organic compounds. The predicted N_{50} increased almost
561 everywhere in continental Europe by $50-300 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. This is 10% increase of N_{50} over central Europe
562 and 20-40% over Scandinavia and northwestern Russia.

563 The addition of IVOC emissions and their aging reactions led to surprising reduction of the
564 total number of particles (N_{tot}) and N_{10} by 10-15 and 5-10%, respectively, and to an increase of the
565 concentration of N_{100} by 5-10%. In this case semi-volatile organic mass is produced, which
566 condenses preferentially on particles in the accumulation mode, increasing the condensation and
567 coagulation sinks and leading to a decrease in the concentration of the sub-10 nm particles.

568

569 **Data and code availability.** Field measurement data are available in ebas.nilu.no and
570 <https://actris.nilu.no/>. The Zeppelin-relevant, San Pietro Capofume and Bologna data are available
571 in <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4660145> (Lampilahti et al. 2021). The field datasets for Patras,
572 Thessaloniki and Costa Navarino can be obtained after request to the authors. The PMCAMx-UF
573 is available from the authors (spyros@chemeng.upatras.gr).

574

575 **Supplement.**

576

577 **Author contributions.** DP wrote the code, conducted the simulations, analyzed the results, and
578 wrote the paper. SNP was responsible for the design of the study and the synthesis of the results
579 and contributed to the writing of the paper.

580

581 **Competing interests.** The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

582

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600

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Table 1: Summary of parameters used in each simulation

CASE	Aging of anthropogenic IVOCs and SVOCs	Source of ELVOCs	Emission of IVOCs
1 (Base case)	Aging with OH $k=10^{-11} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ molecule}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	Monoterpene oxidation 5% molar yield	Yes
2		None	Yes
3		Monoterpene oxidation 5% molar yield	No

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935 **Table 2:** Prediction skill metrics of PMCAMx-UF against daily ground measurements of particle
 936 number concentration above 10 nm (N_{10}) during 5 June – 8 July 2012.
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Station	Mean Observed (cm^{-3})	Mean Predicted (cm^{-3})		NMB (%)		NME(%)	
		Base case	Without ELVOCs	Base case	Without ELVOCs	Base case	Without ELVOCs
N_{10}							
ANB	8057	6617	6585	-18	-18	39	39
ASP	2130	5233	5202	146	144	144	144
BRK	1878	3144	3053	67	63	86	86
CBW	13101	9913	9817	-24	-25	31	31
DSN	10591	6508	6504	-39	-39	41	41
DSW	7706	6111	6091	-21	-21	40	40
FNK	3962	5466	5466	38	38	40	40
GDN	5712	6652	6731	16	18	32	32
HOH	3438	3070	2906	-11	-15	38	38
HYY	2207	2536	2265	15	3	31	31
ISP	6232	6449	6203	3	0	43	43
KPU	5269	5855	5937	11	13	43	43
KST	3596	4881	4834	36	34	46	46
MLP	5583	6034	6003	8	8	42	42
MNT	6455	8364	8273	30	28	45	45
PRG	7272	7281	7273	0	0	44	44
USM	15171	8335	8413	-45	-45	52	52
VAV	3250	8291	8283	155	155	155	155
VRR	1107	1491	1190	35	7	69	57
VSM	2903	7281	7011	151	141	151	141
WLD	4956	7903	7783	59	57	66	64
ZUG	1237	2405	2287	94	85	111	103
NEO	2864	5085	5039	78	76	79	78
PAT	4705	5151	5148	9	9	45	44
SPC	8301	7198	7180	-13	-14	35	35
THE	3894	8577	8530	120	119	120	119
ALL	4820	5957	5889	23	22	63	63

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942 **Table 3:** Prediction skill metrics of PMCAMx-UF against daily ground measurements of particle
 943 number concentration above 100 nm (N_{100}) during 5 June – 8 July 2012.

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Station	Mean Observed (cm^{-3})	Mean Predicted (cm^{-3})		NMB (%)		NME(%)	
		Base case	Without ELVOCs	Base case	Without ELVOCs	Base case	Without ELVOCs
N_{100}							
ANB	1518	939	934	-38	-38	47	47
ASP	552	789	694	43	26	61	51
BRK	607	419	397	-31	-35	65	62
CBW	1627	1550	1441	-5	-11	18	16
DSN	1976	1178	1052	-40	-47	44	49
DSW	1426	1156	1050	-19	-26	35	37
FNK	1760	2383	2330	35	32	39	36
GDN	2492	2797	2826	12	13	34	33
HOH	1011	697	656	-31	-35	37	40
HYY	677	579	445	-14	-34	26	38
ISP	1775	1334	1283	-25	-28	37	38
KPU	1543	1898	1861	23	21	29	28
KST	1123	1138	1061	1	-6	26	21
MLP	1214	1111	977	-9	-20	30	33
MNT	1492	1871	1799	25	21	49	50
PRG	1177	1256	1167	7	-1	26	25
USM	1657	1091	985	-34	-41	40	44
VAV	766	942	899	23	17	48	48
VRR	324	166	90	-49	-72	63	77
VSM	704	747	643	6	-9	34	34
WLD	1116	1063	955	-5	-14	20	23
ZUG	555	555	546	0	-2	44	44
NEO	1489	2041	1971	37	32	45	42
PAT	1747	1765	1766	1	1	21	23
SPC	1702	2051	1978	21	16	36	36
THE	1387	2420	2384	74	72	78	76
ALL	1198	1326	1258	10	5	45	45

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949 **Table 4:** Predicted (PMCAMx-UF) and observed (AMS) average PM₁ concentrations of sulfate,
 950 ammonium and nitrate in different locations for base case simulation.

Station	Sulfate		Ammonium		Nitrate	
	Predicted ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	Observed ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	Predicted ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	Observed ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	Predicted ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	Observed ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)
FIN	4.44	3.50	1.82	1.06	1.00	0.07
PAT	2.83	3.35	1.34	0.95	0.84	0.10
BOL	2.11	2.79	1.08	1.00	0.90	0.60
SPC	2.31	1.81	1.16	0.88	0.99	1.20
ALL	2.99	2.82	1.37	0.97	0.94	0.52

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967 **Table 5:** Prediction skill metrics of PMCAMx-UF base case simulation against daily PM₁ OA
968 measurements.

Station	Mean Predicted ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	Mean Observed ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	NMB (%)	NME (%)	Factor of 2 (%)
FIN	3.19	2.12	50	51	83
PAT	2.75	3.80	-28	28	95
BOL	4.62	5.68	-19	33	74
SPC	4.74	3.98	19	44	77
ALL	3.87	3.79	2	38	82

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971 **Table 6:** Prediction skill metrics of PMCAMx-UF against daily PM_{2.5} OA measurements.

Name	Station	Country	Mean Observed	Mean Predicted	NMB	NME	Factor of 2
			($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	(%)	(%)	(%)
CH02	Payerne	Switzerland	2.54	2.98	17	73	72
DE44	Melpitz	Germany	2.52	4.42	76	88	66
ES1778	Montseny	Spain	4.52	6.28	39	89	59
IT04	Ispra	Italy	5.13	4.41	-14	46	71
PL05	Diabla Gora	Poland	3.64	4.22	16	43	84
SI08	Iskrba	Slovenia	5.98	5.07	-15	33	80
ALL			4.06	4.56	20	62	72

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974 **Figure 1:** Average ground level number concentrations (in cm^{-3}) for the base case simulation
 975 during 5 June – 8 July 2012 for: (a) all particles (N_{tot}); and particles above (b) 10 nm (N_{10}); (c) 50
 976 nm (N_{50}); and (d) 100 nm (N_{100}). Different scales are used.

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978 **Figure 2:** Comparison of predicted PMCAMx-UF (blue line) vs. observed (black dots) vertical
 979 profiles of averaged particle number concentrations for (a) N_{10} and (b) N_{100} of 25 flights over the
 980 Po Valley during the PEGASOS campaign.

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984 **Figure 3:** Average ground level (a) PM_{2.5} ELVOCs mass concentration (in μg m⁻³) and (b) the
985 ratio of the PM_{2.5} mass of ELVOCs to OA during the simulation. Different scales are used.

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 989 **Figure 4:** Average ground level fractional increase (f_{Nx}) of number concentration due to the
 990 condensation of ELVOCs for: (a) all particles (f_{Ntot}); (b) particles above 10 nm (f_{N10}); (c) above 50
 991 nm (f_{N50}); and (d) above 100 nm (f_{N100}). Different scales are used.

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999 **Figure 5:** Average ground level increase of number concentration (in cm^{-3}) due to the
 1000 condensation of ELVOCs for: (a) all particles (ΔN_{tot}); particles above (b) 10 nm (ΔN_{10}); (c) 50 nm
 1001 (ΔN_{50}); and (d) 100 nm (ΔN_{100}). Different scales are used.

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 1008 **Figure 6:** Ground level average (a) increase of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass concentration of organics aerosol (in
 1009 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and (b) fractional increase of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass concentration of organics aerosol (%) due to the
 1010 addition of IVOCs emissions of semi-volatility organic aging, predicted during 5 June – 8 July.
 1011 Different scales are used.

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1025 **Figure 7:** Ground level increase of number concentration (in cm^{-3}) (a-d) and fractional increase
 1026 (f_{Nx}) of number concentration (e-i) due to the addition of IVOCs emissions and aging reactions,
 1027 predicted during 5 June – 8 July 2012 for: (a, e) all particles (N_{tot}); and particles above (b, f) 10 nm
 1028 (N_{10}); (c, g) 50 nm (N_{50}); and (d, i) 100 nm (N_{100}). Different scales are used.

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1032 **Figure 8:** Ground level average increase of number concentration (in cm^{-3}) (a-b-c) and fractional
 1033 increase (f_{N_x}) of number concentration (d-e-f) due to the addition of IVOCs emissions predicted
 1034 during 5 June – 8 July 2012 for: (a, d) particles between 0.8 nm and 10 nm (N_{1-10}); (b, e) particles
 1035 between 10 nm and 50 nm (N_{10-50}) and (c, f) particles between 50 nm and 100 nm (N_{50-100}).
 1036 Different scales are used.